
Streaming Convolutional Attention Models

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Abstract

Recent developments have shown multiple ways to tackle whole-slide image classification with weak labels, a challenging task due to memory constraints. A recent example is Clustering-constrained Attention Multiple instance learning (CLAM), which encodes whole-slide images (WSI) into a smaller set of features. The downside of this approach is that the encoder uses ImageNet pre-trained weights for feature extraction, which might result in suboptimal features for downstream classification tasks. In this study we propose to train the CLAM model end-to-end using streaming stochastic gradient descent, which can train deep neural networks at near static memory cost regardless of image input size. This way the encoder can learn task-specific feature representations of whole-slide images. We show that it is possible to train with images of 65536×65536 at $0.5\mu\text{m}$, and obtain improved results for public datasets of metastasis detection in breast cancer.

1 Introduction

In recent years several efforts have been made to train deep learning networks for classification with whole-slide images (WSIs) in a weakly supervised setting, which means that only a single label is present for the WSI rather than pixel or patch level annotations. The challenge in this setting is to circumvent the memory bottleneck that is imposed due to the sheer size of gigapixel images.

A recent solution is to use Neural Image Compression (NIC), wherein patches are forwarded into an encoder and transformed into a compressed feature space [1, 2]. These embeddings are then stitched and forwarded into a decoder. The CLAM model described in [3] is an example that demonstrates the success of this method. Additionally to neural image compression, the authors added an attention head which pooled the importance of each individual patch using attention values, rather than regular pooling layers. The downside of this approach is that the encoder only uses ImageNet features, which are not necessarily optimal for the pathology domain. While it is possible to train the encoder under NIC, one must resort to patch-wise training which limits the field of view of the encoder, and use unsupervised training schemes, or use patch-level annotations for supervised training [2], which are not always available.

Another group of solutions targets to solve the memory bottleneck directly. In [4] the authors developed a method called Streaming Stochastic Gradient Descent (SSGD) to train a neural network, which exploits the locality property of convolutions by not holding the entire feature map in memory, but by reconstructing the gradients of the WSI through repeatedly running forward and backward

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed method: **a.** A compact representation of the WSI is created by packing tissues in a rectangle with minimal area. **b.** The CLAM architecture when trained with SSGD. The entire WSI is forwarded to a ResNet-34 encoder, the feature maps are then masked to filter out residual white space. The resulting embeddings are then passed to the CLAM attention block. **c.** The original WSI with breast cancer annotations (left) the attention maps generated by the model (middle), and the attention map overlaid on the original wsi (right).

passes on overlapping tiles. Using this method, the authors were able to train CNN architectures with gigapixel images directly [5]. Another method uses unified memory by swapping between the GPU and RAM memory, which extends the total available memory in a similar way to virtual memory [6]. However, this method does require terabytes of memory to be available to work for Gigapixel images, and is therefore not practical in many situations.

In this study we propose to use SSGD on the CLAM architecture. The original implementation still left ample room for improvement, since the encoder uses pre-trained ImageNet weights. Using SSGD we can train the entire architecture end-to-end and fine-tune the encoder with richer feature representations and apply it to detect breast cancer metastases in (H&E) stained whole-slide images. We compare our approach to that of [3] and [1].

2 Methods

CLAM follows an encoder-decoder structure where patches are passed into a ResNet-50 encoder, which turns the patches into vectors. These vectors are then stitched together into a single embedding, which is then passed into a decoder, consisting of several fully connected layers and attention branches. Optionally, an instance level clustering task can be performed, which we did not use. In this study we train the entire CLAM network end-to-end using SSGD. The most significant change is that the entire model is trained on WSI inputs directly, without going through patches first. A full diagram is displayed in figure 1.

We change the encoder backbone from a ResNet-50 to a ResNet-34, since the latter network takes less time to train using SSGD. Secondly, we replace the global average pooling layer at the end of the network by a max pooling layer, with kernel sizes and strides specified in table 1. Since the entire WSI is forwarded at once, a global pooling layer would result in too much downsampling.

We also add an optional masking operation at the end of the encoder to filter out any white spaces before being passed on to the decoder, which decreases the number of input neurons. We use a tissue background segmentation algorithm [7] to generate the tissue masks.

Training details To speed up training we use a two stage approach. First, we freeze the encoder and only train the decoder until convergence. We then continue from the model with the lowest cross entropy loss on the tuning set and train the entire model, including the encoder. Both stages use an Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $1e - 4$ and $1e - 5$, respectively. A mini-batch size of 16 is used. We initialize the networks using ImageNet-trained weights for the encoder. The decoder weights are initialized using Glorot [8], which is the same as in the original implementation of [3]. Mixed-precision training is used to speed up the training process.

To reduce the white space in the training images, we extract bounding boxes around the tissue samples inside of the WSI, and place these boxes in a rectangle with minimal area. The resulting images are

Table 1: Results for breast cancer metastases detection. Mean AUC and accuracy scores with 95% CI based on 2000 bootstrapping results. s : max pool stride, k : max pool kernel size. ps : patch size. In all CLAM models, the step size is equal to the patch size, so there is no overlap between patches.

	Size (μm)	AUC	Accuracy	Notes
Camelyon16				
CLAM	1.0	0.7680 [0.6824, 0.8482]	0.8056 [0.7442, 0.8605]	$ps=128$
CLAM	0.5	0.8634 [0.7994, 0.9221]	0.8521 [0.7984, 0.907]	$ps=256$
CLAM	0.25	0.9504 [0.9191, 0.977]	0.8906 [0.845, 0.938]	$ps=512$
NIC [1]	0.5	0.704	-	
SSGD CLAM	1.0	0.7972 [0.7110, 0.8781]	0.8523 [0.7984, 0.8992]	$s=4, k=(4,4)$
SSGD CLAM	0.5	0.9834 [0.9641, 0.9995]	0.9690 [0.9457, 0.9922]	$s=8, k=(8,8)$
<hr/>				
CNN-RF [10]	0.25	0.994	-	leaderboard 1st, pixel annotations
CNN-RF [10]	0.25	0.976	-	leaderboard 2nd, pixel annotations
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Camelyon17				
CLAM	0.5	0.9057 [0.8791, 0.9316]	0.7860 [0.7560, 0.816]	$ps=256$
CLAM	0.25	0.9040 [0.8775, 0.928]	0.7937 [0.7640, 0.822]	$ps=512$
SSGD CLAM	0.5	0.9306 [0.9037, 0.9557]	0.8938 [0.8700, 0.916]	$s=8, k=(8,8)$

either padded or cropped to fit into a square image. The image sizes during training with SSGD are 32768×32768 and 65536×65536 for $1\mu\text{m}$ and $0.5\mu\text{m}$, respectively. We stream the entire ResNet-34 up to but not including the final max pooling layer introduced in section 2. The rest of the network is trained with regular backpropagation. Batch normalization cannot be used for the streaming part of the network, as it requires computing global statistics on an entire feature map. Therefore, we froze the batch normalization layers and use the normalization statistics from ImageNet.

3 Experiments

We train and evaluate our approach on the Camelyon16 dataset [9], which consists of 399 H&E slides of breast cancer lymph node metastasis. 270 slides can be used for training and validation, and the remaining 129 are used for testing. We modified the labels to perform a binary classification consisting of either tumor or no tumor by assigning the negative cases to no tumor, and the micro/macro cases to the tumor class. The area-under-the-receiver-operating curve (AUC) and accuracy are used as evaluation metrics. Additionally, we use the training portion of the Camelyon17 dataset as an extra test set, consisting of 500 slides. Isolated tumor cells are counted as negative cases, following [3]. During training we oversampled tumor cases to deal with the imbalance in the dataset. For regularization, we applied an augmentation strategy consisting of elastic deformation, random vertical and horizontal flips, rotations, and color augmentations by perturbing the HSV color space. These augmentations are only applied during the second training stage. During test time, we average the weights around the lowest validation loss with a window of 5 epochs.

4 Results and Discussion

In this study we investigated the effect of training end-to-end models. The results in table 1 indicate that the CLAM architecture can substantially benefit from training the encoder with SSGD, as it is able to learn task-specific feature representations while maintaining full field of view of the entire WSI. Furthermore, our method obtains competitive results even when it is not evaluated at full resolution ($0.25\mu\text{m}$).

The main limitation from the proposed method is that it is computationally intensive. With large inputs, the CPU memory along with time constraints become the primary bottleneck. Therefore, training on consumer grade machines might prove challenging at higher resolutions. A point of improvement is to use networks that do not have aggressive downsampling at the early stages of the encoder. The use of early downsampling prohibits the encoder from extracting relevant but tiny features, such as micro metastasis. A possible alternative would be to use a MobileNetV2 [11] architecture, which distributes the downsampling more evenly across the network.

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